

Adaptation of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages to sign languages Challenges, limitations and the possibilities of empirical, multidisciplinary research and partnership

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Assessing knowledge of language and language skills plays an important role not only in L1 education but also in L2 education, so it is no surprise that there has been an increasing demand for adapting the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) to sign languages during the past years. However, in the case of visual modality sign languages it is a question whether the system developed explicitly for written and spoken versions of spoken languages is applicable or not, and if yes, to what extent. One of the biggest challenges is the lack of literacy, another challenge is the detailed, precise and sign language based grammatical description of the important elements of meaning construction of sign languages (such as grammatical function of space, non-manual elements etc.), furthermore, sign language curricula should not only be evidence-based, but they have to capture various aspects of sign language use as well. Our presentation highlights the issues of the adaptability of CEFR building on the recent results and experiences of corpus research, dictionary construction and standardization for educational purposes of the Hungarian Sign Language.